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- 13.00.01 Pedagogika nazariyasi. Pedagogik ta'limotlar tarixi
- 13.00.02 Ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi (sohalar bo'yicha)
- 13.00.03 Maxsus pedagogika
- 13.00.04 Jismoniy tarbiya va sport mashg'ulotlari nazariyasi va metodikasi
- 13.00.05 Kasb-hunar ta'limi nazariyasi va metodikasi
- 13.00.06 Elektron ta'lim nazariyasi va metodikasi (ta'lim sohaları va bosqichlari bo'yicha)
- 13.00.07 Ta'limda menejment
- 13.00.08 Maktabgacha ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi
- 13.00.09 Ijtimoiy pedagogika
- 07.00.00 Tarix fanlari
- 19.00.00 Psixologiya fanlari
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- 03.00.00 Biologiya fanlari
- 09.00.00 Falsafa fanlari
- 10.00.00 Filologiya fanlari
- 11.00.00 Geografiya fanlari

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PRAGMALINGUODIDACTIC PRINCIPLES IN TEACHING ENGLISH FOR PHILOLOGIST STUDENTS AND THEIR APPLICATION IN INTERCULTURAL COMMUNICATION

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Abstract: This article examines the theoretical and methodological foundations of pragmalinguodidactic principles for teaching English to philology students within Uzbek and Karakalpak linguocultural contexts. The study identifies five core principles—pragmatization of communicative activity, consideration of language development tendencies, and comprehension of the functional-stylistic register. These principles necessitate teaching English in alignment with contemporary lexical shifts, global digital discourse, and authentic instructional materials. Their implementation supports the integration of the pragmatic features of the English language with Uzbek and Karakalpak cultural norms in the process of teaching English at the CEFR C1 level.

Key words: pragmalinguodidactics; intercultural communication; communicative competence; stylistic register; linguo-pragmatics; teaching English; CEFR C1.

Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqola o'zbek va qoraqalpoq lingvomadaniy sharoitida filologiya yo'nalishidagi talabalarga ingliz tilini o'qitishda pragmalingvodidaktik tamoyillarning nazariy-metodologik asoslarini tahlil qiladi. Tadqiqotda kommunikativ faoliyatni pragmatizatsiyalash, til rivojlanishi tendensiyalarini hisobga olish va funksional-stilistik registri anglash kabi besh asosiy tamoyil aniqlanadi. Mazkur tamoyillar ingliz tilini zamonaviy leksik o'zgarishlar, global raqamli diskurs hamda autentik materiallar bilan uyg'un holda o'qitishni talab etadi. Ularning qo'llanilishi ingliz tilining pragmatik xususiyatlarini o'zbek va qoraqalpoq madaniy me'yorlari bilan uyg'unlashtirish orqali CEFR C1 darajasida samarali o'qitishga xizmat qiladi.

Kalit so'zlar: pragmalingvodidaktika; madaniyatlararo kommunikatsiya; kommunikativ kompetensiya; stilistik registr; lingvopragmatika; ingliz tilini o'qitish; CEFR C1.

Аннотация: В статье рассматриваются теоретико-методологические основы прагмалингводидактических принципов преподавания английского языка студентам-филологам в узбекском и каракалпакском лингвокультурном контексте. Определяются пять ключевых принципов: прагматизация коммуникативной деятельности, учет тенденций развития языка и осмысление функционально-стилистического регистра. Реализация данных принципов предполагает обучение английскому языку в соответствии с современными лексическими изменениями, глобальным цифровым дискурсом и использованием аутентичных материалов. Применение этих принципов способствует гармонизации прагматических особенностей английского языка с узбекскими и каракалпакскими культурными нормами при обучении на уровне CEFR C1.

Ключевые слова: прагмалингводидактика; межкультурная коммуникация; коммуникативная компетенция; стилистический регистр; лингвопрагматика; преподавание английского языка; CEFR C1.

INTRODUCTION

One of the central tasks of pragmalinguodidactics is to define and substantiate its fundamental principles. To address this, we formulated a system of pragmalinguodidactic principles for foreign language teaching, building on established linguodidactic principles and taking into account the pragmatization of philology students' speech through modern linguistic means. These principles serve as the theoretical and methodological basis for developing intercultural communication competence in philology students, as they harmonize the pragmatic component of language instruction with cultural context and enable learners to apply communicative activity in a foreign language within real-life situations.

LITERATURE REVIEW

In foreign language communicative activity, language functions as a tool for personality development within specific social and situational contexts. This principle is essential for forming intercultural communication competence in philology students because it focuses not on linguistic forms themselves, but on their culturally and pragmatically conditioned use. I.I. Khaleeva identifies four macro-spheres of communication: the sphere of production (material-practical) activity, the sphere of daily and domestic relations, the sphere of culture (artistic and scientific creativity), and the sphere of social life defined by socio-political activity ^[8]. Across all these domains, individuals employ language as a means of achieving their pragmatic goals.

According to G.K. Tazhimbetova, in a pedagogical setting the teacher imparts linguistic knowledge and forms pragmatic competence through speech acts and communicative strategies; however, insufficient explicit instruction of these elements in Uzbekistan negatively affects pedagogical effectiveness and contradicts CEFR requirements [3]. This view aligns with the theoretical and methodological foundations of the pragmalinguo-didactic approach to developing intercultural communication competence in philology students, as it clearly outlines the linguistic, cognitive, and interactive criteria of pragmatic competence in pedagogical speech and demonstrates the potential for integrating these criteria with CEFR levels (B2–C1). Thus, pragmatizing the oral speech of philology students in a foreign language requires the use of linguistic features characteristic of modern English, which, in turn, demands that teachers deliberately select authentic materials and design appropriate methods for working with them.

Pragmalinguistic research shows that language is constantly evolving, and the “image of a living language” in the 21st century no longer corresponds to traditional textbooks. This principle promotes students’ adaptation to real communication through exposure to internet discourse and modern media. In Uzbekistan’s context, authentic materials from platforms such as YouTube and TikTok, as well as dynamic lexical modules (including slang and memes), are incorporated into the teaching process to enhance students’ pragmatic sensitivity and cultural adaptability. Modern English has witnessed the emergence of numerous new lexical items—neologisms and abbreviations—whose usage depends on context, stylistic register, and pragmatic function. Therefore, the primary educational objective should be the development of pragmatic competence through adapting new lexical units to functional—stylistic registers and learning their normative usage ^[3].

Researcher G.K. Tazhimbetova further notes that foreign language proficiency requirements in pedagogical activity rely heavily on the teaching of speech acts. The core principles of this approach include:

- (1) functionality and interactivity;
- (2) modeling pedagogical communication situations with interdisciplinary connections;
- (3) ensuring that exercises correspond to the characteristics of speech acts and interactive patterns;
- (4) a cognitive approach to studying speech acts while accounting for interference-related difficulties;
- (5) modulation and minimization of instructional content; and
- (6) consistency and adequacy in the design of exercises ^[3].

The researcher developed a methodological model for forming pragmatic competence in future teachers, enabling them to meet foreign language proficiency requirements in pedagogical contexts (e.g., CEFR B2–C1 levels) through explicit teaching of speech acts such as requests, questions, explanations, instructions, praise, evaluation, and criticism.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The principle of taking into account the functional—stylistic register of speech plays an essential role in the process of learning a foreign language. A student must learn to understand the “semantic mechanisms of interaction” characteristic of native speakers ^[7]. Therefore, it is important to teach learners to select and use the appropriate functional—stylistic register in various communicative relations, to navigate the communicative—pragmatic space, and to orient themselves within the cultural environment. Communicators belonging to different cultures may fail to reach mutual understanding or may face intercultural misunderstandings, since culturally diverse societies adopt distinct discourse patterns and speech norms even for identical communicative situations. Miscommunication often arises when interlocutors unknowingly apply a speech register that does not correspond to the communicative context or cultural norms of the interaction.

For instance, in asymmetrical social relationships—where hierarchy is clearly established—informal expressions or simplified speech forms are not acceptable in formal, high-status settings requiring strict adherence to communication norms. Conversely, in informal, personal, or highly familiar interactions, the use of simple,

colloquial expressions is considered natural and appropriate. Researcher U. R. Kadyrov proposes that effective cultural teaching of English should integrate several pedagogical principles: language–culture interconnectedness, cultural competence, cognitive, comparative, communicative, interactive, contextual, visual, and design-based principles [2]. In our view, modern cultural–pragmatic developments in the English-speaking world—such as the evolution of the expression “Cheers” in social media discourse—play a significant role in developing the pragmatic dimension of intercultural communication competence in philology students. Considering language development trends as one of the core principles of the pragmalinguodidactic approach enables the analysis of the dynamic evolution of language within its cultural–pragmatic context, helping philology students form a deeper level of intercultural communication competence. In U. R. Kadyrov’s cultural approach, the principles of language–culture unity, the development of cultural competence (e.g., the cultural significance of “Thanksgiving”), comparative analysis (Ramadan vs. Christmas), contextual interpretation (“Cheers” within dining traditions), and design-based tasks (holiday/dinner projects) collectively reveal the cultural dimension of language development [2]. Through the integration of these principles, philology students develop dynamic intercultural competence: for example, alongside the semantic meaning of “Cheers,” its pragmatic function as an expressive speech act is analyzed in contemporary contexts. Such analysis enhances the pragmatic effectiveness of intercultural communication and reflects the influence of global linguistic trends.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

In the textbooks, there is an evident lack of authentic pragmatic texts representing various spheres of communication, including social-domestic, socio-cultural, professional-labor, civic activity, administrative-legal, recreational, and interest-based interactions. The integration of authentic pragmatic materials into the educational process enables students to develop communicative competence across different registers of speech. IV. The boundary principle of stylistic decline in speech. When analyzing the relationship between language and linguistic culture, it is important to protect language users from the excessive and often inappropriate use of linguistic innovations, transformations, abbreviations, foreign borrowings, and simplified phraseological units. In recent years, especially among the youth, a noticeable inclination has emerged to “decorate” their native language with an unnecessary abundance of such linguistic elements, leading to a sharp stylistic decline and overall coarsening of speech.

Language fashion affects all languages globally. For example, in English, many traditional expressions have been replaced by new, more colloquial alternatives:

- to telephone (to call) → to give somebody a buzz (“Give me a buzz the next time you are going to town.”);
- to be in a difficult situation → to be in a fix (“I told her that someday she would be in a pretty fix.”);
- in a moment/very quickly → in a jiffy (“I’ll have it fixed in a jiffy.”);
- there’s no pleasure/it’s difficult → it’s no picnic (“It’s no picnic to work there.”).

These examples demonstrate the global nature of language fashion and linguistic change—an aspect highly relevant to the training of philology students. Studying such linguistic trends within a pragmalinguodidactic framework fosters the development of students’ sociolinguistic awareness.

As society evolves, new lexical units emerge as well. For instance, the term “disadvantaged” appeared to mitigate economic inequality; “coloured” or “non-white” began to replace “black” to reduce racial discrimination; academically weak students began to be labeled “underachievers.” Similarly, individuals born under the constellation Cancer are sometimes referred to as “moon-child” to avoid associations with illness. V. The principle of complementarity in intercultural communication within the audience context. A key characteristic of intercultural communication in university-level foreign language instruction is its training-oriented nature, as students belong to the same cultural background and study the target language outside its natural environment, distanced from real communicative practices [4]. Z.S. Poziljonova notes: “There exist several types of nonverbal communication, such as proxemics, tactilics, kinesics, sensonics, and chronemics. Moreover, rhythm, timbre, speed, phraseological and logical pacing constitute paraverbal modes of communication” [1]. Incorporating such communicative elements into speech-oriented instruction is crucial for developing philology students’ intercultural communicative competence.

In foreign language teaching, authentic materials (podcasts, videos, texts) represent an essential resource for ensuring exposure to real intercultural contexts. However, their linguodidactic adaptation to the national educational environment—particularly to the realities of the Uzbek and Karakalpak languages—is necessary. The study highlights the importance of critically analyzing and culturally evaluating authentic materials because they differ in purpose, contain specific pragmatic content, and evoke diverse cultural responses among learners.

Variations in age, social background, and cultural context of the materials do not always align with educational requirements. Achieving CEFR C1 (“Professional Skills”) proficiency in English presupposes the ability to express thoughts spontaneously and almost effortlessly. At this level, learners possess a sufficiently extensive lexical repertoire, enabling them to select appropriate vocabulary according to context. When introducing new words or constructions, C1-level students should be able to incorporate them naturally and fluently; only conceptually complex topics may challenge this ability^[6]. Therefore, the use of modern teaching methods, updated lexical material, and texts representing all three registers of speech (formal, neutral, and informal) becomes indispensable.

CONCLUSION

In this study, five pragmalinguodidactic principles – the pragmatization of communicative skills, consideration of English language development, attention to speech registers, the boundary of stylistic reduction, and intercultural support – were practically implemented in the development of intercultural communication competence at the C1 level of English proficiency. Applying these principles enables the prevention of pragmatic errors by conducting a parallel comparison of English pragmatic implicatures with the cultural norms inherent in the Uzbek and Karakalpak languages.

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- 13.00.00 Pedagogika fanlari
 - 13.00.01 Pedagogika nazariyasi. Pedagogik ta'limotlar tarixi
 - 13.00.02 Ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi (sohalar bo'yicha)
 - 13.00.03 Maxsus pedagogika
 - 13.00.04 Jismoniy tarbiya va sport mashg'ulotlari nazariyasi va metodikasi
 - 13.00.05 Kasb-hunar ta'limi nazariyasi va metodikasi
 - 13.00.06 Elektron ta'lim nazariyasi va metodikasi (ta'lim sohaları va bosqichlari bo'yicha)
 - 13.00.07 Ta'limda menejment
 - 13.00.08 Maktabgacha ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi
 - 13.00.09 Ijtimoiy pedagogika
 - 07.00.00 Tarix fanlari
 - 19.00.00 Psixologiya fanlari
 - 01.00.00 Fizika-matematika fanlari
 - 02.00.00 Kimyo fanlari
 - 03.00.00 Biologiya fanlari
 - 09.00.00 Falsafa fanlari
 - 10.00.00 Filologiya fanlari
 - 11.00.00 Geografiya fanlari

MAKTABGACHA VA MAKTAB TA'LIMI

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